

Sieving Varietal Resistance in Bread Wheat Cultivars and Chemical Control Efficacy Against *Schizaphis graminum* R.

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ABSTRACT

Current field trial was conducted to screen out varietal resistance against wheat aphid (*Schizaphis graminum* R.) in four wheat cultivars viz. Galaxy-2013, Punjab-2011, Millat-2011 and Sehar-2006 and comparative toxicity of three synthetic insecticides (pymetrozine 50 WG, imidacloprid 20 SL and lambda-cyhalothrin 2.5 EC) was also evaluated through foliar application at their recommended doses. Aphid infestation started in last week of January, reached on its peak on 15th of March and vanished up to 10th April. The most resistant wheat cultivar with minimum aphid infestation was Galaxy-2013 (18 ± 0.49 mean aphids/tiller); whereas, Sehar-2006 (27 ± 0.29 mean aphids/tiller) came out as most susceptible among other cultivars. Imidacloprid appeared to be most effective and persistent insecticide with maximum aphid mortality i.e. 97.13% (1.26 aphids/tiller), fourteen days after treatment. Tenacity of imidacloprid was also justified by wheat grains analysis through HPLC technique for insecticides residual toxicity with maximum limit of detection i.e. 0.005 mg kg⁻¹, which is negligible as compared to WHO standards for maximum residual limits. This study concluded that Galaxy-2013 is a resistant wheat cultivar and with the judicious use of imidacloprid it can be used as worthy tools in IPM to keep aphid population below than economic injury level.

Key words: Wheat, Varietal resistance, wheat aphid (*Schizaphis graminum*), insecticides, Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Food security is one of the major concerns of today world leaders. Cereal grains are imperative source of calories and proteins [1]. Bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) a high calorie food, has a primal role in ensuring food security due to high nutritious contents and versatile natures of plants under the changing set of climatic conditions [2]. A common man meets 60% of his food requirement from wheat utilization [3]. The FAO (food and agriculture organization) prognosis for world cereal reserves has been dropped by 3 million tons since the previous report to 631 million tons by the close of 2016, mostly owing to wheat. Wheat is predisposed to contamination by a range of insects which can cause undesirable levels of quality deterioration of the grain [4]. Many factors are responsible for low yield of wheat in Pakistan but insect pests play a key role. Aphid (Aphididae: Homoptera) is an important sucking pest of various field crops including wheat, barley, sorghum and corn with range of species, sometimes called as plant louse [2]. Aphid is the supreme detrimental agent to wheat among other insects [5]. It harms bread wheat by sucking sap and injecting toxins into the plant, causing direct feeding damage to leaves, stem and developing kernels and destroys plant tissue [6]. Aphid impedes with grain formation by injecting a poisonous material into plant parts [7]. (Geza, 2000) [8] Found 29 aphid species among flying insect on wheat. Now aphid has become a regular pest of wheat in Pakistan due to dramatic intensification in its population which is responsible for losses to economic yield up to 35 to 40% directly by sucking the cell

sap of the plants or 20 to 80% indirectly by diffusing fungal and viral infections [9].

There are plenty of ways to control aphid's infestation below economic injury level like, physical, mechanical, chemical, biological, cultural, and resistance in host plant controls. But biological control plays a significant role in lessening of insect's population. Aphid incidence varies among different wheat cultivars and also depends on crop stage [10]. In the nearest past some species of aphids have gained a position of exceptional pests. Under sustainable and good environmental conditions, wheat aphids reproduce at a much quicker rate which causes infestation of 1-3 % of total production of wheat in the whole world [11]. Many control measures including varietal resistance are adopted in Integrated Pest Management (IPM) to keep aphid population under economic injury level; however, sometimes chemicals have to be used for control when aphid outbreak is extremely injurious [12]. Use of those selective insecticides which have the least possible detrimental effect on predator of aphids could be the finest choice.

Present study was, there for, conducted to sieve varietal resistance in three new wheat cultivars as compared to an old susceptible wheat cultivar and to check efficacy of some synthetic insecticides against *Schizaphis graminum* was tested.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant method and experimental details

Four bread wheat cultivars viz. Galaxy-2013, Punjab-2011, Millat-2011 and Sehar-2006 were sown at Entomological research area, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad (31.41°N

latitude and 73.08°E longitude, Faisalabad, Pakistan) on November 22, 2014 following randomized complete block design with three replications. The net size of each experimental unit was 8 × 1.2 m². Insecticides (Pymetrozine 50 WG@ 200 gm ha⁻¹, Imidacloprid 20 SL@ 625 ml ha⁻¹ and Lambda-cyhalothrin 2.5 EC@ 625 ml ha⁻¹) were sprayed by knapsack hand sprayer when population of wheat aphids reached the economic threshold level (ETL).

Data regarding aphid population were recorded 5±2 day's interval started from last week of January till 1st week of April by counting of aphids from 15 randomly selected wheat plants. After crop harvesting, mature wheat grains were analyzed through High Performance liquid Chromatography (HPLC) for insecticides residues. Data collected on various attributes were statistically analyzed using fisher's ANOVA technique using "DAASTAT" statistical program [13]. Difference among

treatments means was compared using Fisher's least significant test (LSD) at 5% probability level [14].

RESULTS

Aphid population dynamics study revealed varying level of resistance in different wheat cultivars. Aphid first appeared on Sehar-2006 due to better vegetative growth as compared to other cultivars, with mean aphid population per tiller (0.33 ± 0.03) sixty three DAS during last week of January. The gradual increase in aphid population continued until 15th of March when population reached on its peak 112 DAS. On 15th March mean aphid population per tiller varied significantly among all wheat cultivars except Punjab-2011 and Millat-2011 (73.13±1.44 and 70.93±2.93, respectively), maximal aphid population was recorded on Sehar-2006 (81.43±1.43 aphids/tiller) and minimum on Galaxy-2013 (59.37±3.68 aphids/tiller) as shown in table 1.

Table 1. Aphid population (means) tiller⁻¹ plant⁻¹ on various wheat cultivars at different dates of observations

Varieties	Aphid population on different dates											Means ± S.E
	1/2	7/2	14/2	21/2	28/2	8/3	15/3	22/3	29/3	5/4	10/4	
Galaxy-2013	0.40 c	2.03 c	13.53 c	22.53 c	33.13 c	43.57 c	59.37c	38.33 b	25.57 b	10.17 b	1.23 b	18±0.49 c
Punjab-2011	0.53 b	2.30 b	15.70b	29.50 b	47.43a b	55.90 b	73.13a b	37.67 b	23.50 b	8.63b	0.10 c	21±0.38 b
Millat-2011	0.50 b	2.43 b	15.87b	30.67 b	42.10b c	48.23 c	70.93b	40.53 b	24.33 b	9.43b	0.27 c	21±0.49 b
Sehar-2006	1.23 a	4.03 a	22.77a	41.23 a	52.83a	64.13 a	81.43a	56.93 a	34.03 a	13.83 a	1.93 a	27±0.29 a
LSD value	0.18	0.26	1.89	2.88	9.11	5.97	9.65	5.72	2.87	2.38	0.68	1.25

Each value is mean of 3 replications. Means sharing same letters are not significantly different from each other by Fisher's LSD test at P= 0.05.

After 1st week of April rapid decline in aphid population occurred in all cultivars and population eliminated up to 10th April; however, mid of March appeared to be most satisfactory period for growth of aphid and displayed maximum aphid population (Fig.1).

Figure 1. Aphid population fluctuation at different dates during year 2014

Fig. 2 shows that Galaxy-2013 came out as most resistant wheat cultivar with minimum aphid population (18±0.49 mean aphids/tiller) and Sehar-2006 as most susceptible (27±0.29 mean aphids/tiller); however, Punjab-2011 and Millat-2011 were not statistically different from each other at (df = 3; F = 113.06; P ≤ 0.05) with mean aphid populations (21±0.38 and 21±0.49 aphids/tiller, respectively).

Figure 2. Mean aphid population on various wheat cultivars at P = 0.05

Impact of insecticides treatment on aphid population

It is evident from results (Table 2) that all three insecticides i.e. pymetrozine, imidacloprid and lambda-cyhalothrin reduced aphid population significantly as compared to control.

Aphid population 24 hours after spray

Maximum aphid population (43.87/tiller) was recorded on control plot with no insecticides application followed by pymetrozine (4.54/tiller), imidacloprid (3.33/tiller) and lambda-cyhalothrin (1.23/tiller) as shown in table 2. Lambda-cyhalothrin caused maximum aphid mortality (97.21%) and pymetrozine (89.65%) appeared with minimum control (Fig 3).

Aphid population 48 hours after spray

Untreated plots appeared to be most susceptible with mean population 44.78 aphids per tiller. Non-significant difference was found in all treatments and mean aphid population ranged between 0.17 to 0.53 aphids per tiller (Table 2). Graphical

presentation in fig. 3 reveals that maximum percentage mortality was recorded by lambda-cyhalothrin (99.62%) and minimum by pymetrozine (98.78%).

Table 2. Aphid population (means) per tiller of *Schizaphisgraminum* on different intervals post treatment of insecticides on wheat

Treatments	Aphid density				Mean ± S.E
	1 DAT	2 DAT	7 DAT	14 DAT	
Control (Untreated)	43.87a	44.78a	52.96a	71.22a	31.19±2.54 a
Pymetrozine	4.54b	0.53b	1.38b	5.67b	2.66±0.21 b
Imidacloprid	3.33b	0.30b	0.51b	1.26b	1.84±0.16 b
Lambda-Cyhalothrin	1.23b	0.17b	0.45b	3.16b	1.93±0.15 b
LSD Value	1.84	1.70	1.1	2.56	0.55

Means sharing similar letters are not significantly different by Fisher's LSD test at $P = 0.05$.

DAT = Days after treatment

Aphid population 7 days after spray

Lambda-cyhalothrin and imidacloprid caused almost same percentage mortality i.e. 98.97% (0.45 aphids/tiller) and 98.84% (0.51 aphids/tiller); however, pymetrozine appeared to give minimum control and caused 96.85% mortality with 1.38 aphids per tiller (Fig 3). All three insecticides were persistent and gave satisfactory control 7 days after spray but, non-significantly different from each other as compared to untreated plots (71.22 aphids/tiller) as shown in table 2.

Aphid population 14 days after spray

The results of this study (Table 2) clearly reveal that imidacloprid was most effective against *Schizaphisgraminum* with 1.26 aphids per tiller 14 days after treatment and induced 97.13% mortality. In addition lambda-cyhalothrin and pymetrozine also suppressed aphid population effectively i.e. 3.16 and 5.67 aphids per tiller, respectively. Aphid Percentage mortality was reduced by lambda-cyhalothrin (92.80%) and pymetrozine (87.80%).

Mean aphid population after four intervals observations post treatment of insecticides indicated significant variation among treatments on different wheat cultivars. In untreated plots mean aphid population was recorded minimum on Galaxy-2013

(24.88/tiller) and maximum on Sehar-2006 (37.01/tiller). All three insecticides were more effective on Galaxy-2013 i.e. imidacloprid (1.55/tiller), lambda-cyhalothrin (1.65 aphids/tiller) and pymetrozine (2.32aphids/tiller), against *S. graminum* as compared to other wheat cultivars as is shown in table 3. Overall, aphid population was suppressed significantly by all three insecticides but, imidacloprid as a systemic insecticide appeared to be most persistent and effective followed by lambda-cyhalothrin and pymetrozine (Fig 3).

Figure 3. Graphical presentation regarding mean aphids population on various wheat cultivars influenced by different insecticides. Means sharing similar letter are not significantly different at $P = 0.05$.

Table 3. Mean aphid population on various wheat cultivars influenced by different insecticides

Varieties	Treatments	Means±S.E
Galaxy-2013	Control (Untreated)	24.88 ± 0.39 d
	Pymetrozine	2.32 ± 0.10 ef
	Imidacloprid	1.55 ± 0.07 f
	Lambda-Cyhalothrin	1.65 ± 0.15 f
Punjab-2011	Control (Untreated)	32.78 ± 1.08 b
	Pymetrozine	2.52 ± 0.07 ef
	Imidacloprid	1.68 ± 0.05 f
	Lambda-Cyhalothrin	1.72 ± 0.14 f
Millat-2011	Control (Untreated)	30.10 ± 0.37 c
	Pymetrozine	2.53 ± 0.19 ef
	Imidacloprid	1.85 ± 0.04 f
	Lambda-Cyhalothrin	2.02 ± 0.11 f
Sehar-2006	Control (Untreated)	37.01 ± 0.12 a
	Pymetrozine	3.27 ± 0.01 ef
	Imidacloprid	2.29 ± 0.09 ef

	Lambda-Cyhalothrin	2.32 ± 0.18ef
LSD value		1.10

Means sharing similar letters are not significantly different from each other by Fisher's LSD test at P = 0.05.

Figure 4. Percentage mortality of *Schizaphisgraminum* by three insecticides on different time intervals.

Residual toxicity of insecticides in mature wheat grains

Samples of wheat grains from different treatments viz. pymetrozine, imidacloprid and lambda-cyhalothrin were analyzed for residual toxicity by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) technique at Nuclear Institute for Agriculture and Biology (NIAB), Faisalabad. According to results dispatched limit of detection in three insecticides i.e. pymetrozine, lambda-cyhalothrin and imidacloprid was 0.002, 0.003 and 0.005 mg kg⁻¹, respectively. This limit of detection was negligible as compared to international standard for maximum residual limit (MRL) in wheat by World health organization (WHO) and Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) i.e. 0.03, 0.05 and 0.05 mg kg⁻¹ for imidacloprid, pymetrozine and lambda-cyhalothrin, respectively [15].

DISCUSSION

According to the results of present study, aphid appeared in last week of January (63 DAS), and gradual increase in population continued up to 3rd week of February. Fourth week of February favored aphid multiplication and its population reached to its peak in mid-March with only one swarming peak. Decline in aphid population was observed at the end of March and population vanished in 2nd week of April. Present results are in confirmatory with those of [16], [17] and [18]. Contrarily, three swarming peaks of aphid population were observed by [19] and [5] who found aphid population peak in 4th week of April in Arid zone. These differences might be due to dissimilar environmental conditions of the experimental sites.

Considerably, none of the wheat cultivars was found resistant against wheat aphids; however, moderately resistant wheat cultivars showed minimum aphid population as compared to susceptible wheat cultivars. All four cultivars i.e. Galaxy-2013, Punjab-2011, Millat-2011 and Sehar-2006 were significantly different from each other regarding varietal resistance against *Schizaphisgraminum*. These outcomes are in favor with those of [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25] and [26], who found varying levels of resistance in different wheat cultivars; however, [27] studied the resistance of 16 wheat advanced lines/varieties to *Schizaphisgraminum* and reported, that test entries showed non-significant difference due to low aphid population and were statistically at par with one another.

Imidacloprid appeared to be most persistent 14 days after insecticides application sustaining 97.13% aphid mortality followed by lambda-cyhalothrin (92.80%) and pymetrozine

(87.08%). All insecticides significantly reduced aphid incidence in treated plots than that in the control (untreated) but, these were not statistically different from each other. The results of present study are same with those of Joshi and Sharma, (2009) [28] and (Shahzad *et al.*, 2013) [29], who used imidacloprid 200 SL @ 400 and 100 ml ha⁻¹ for foliar application against wheat aphid and found significant control as compared to other insecticides. (Royer *et al.*, 2013) [30] Used three insecticides i.e. dimethoate, chlorpyrifos and lambda-cyhalothrin against green bugs, Insect control was temperature dependent and ranging from 0% to 95%. dimethoate was the most effective with aphid population suppression from 16% to 96.9%; however, its efficacy reduced by rainfall but other two pesticides remained persistent. The results of present research were not related to [31], [32], [33]; because, wheat aphid species were other than *Schizaphisgraminum* and insecticides used by them were dissimilar i.e. pirimicarb @ 100 and 300 g a.i ha⁻¹, chlorpyrifos @ 5 ml L⁻¹, thiamethoxam diluted concentrations of 0.0005, 0.005, 0.05, 0.5, 1.5, 2.5 and 5 mg L⁻¹, thiamethoxam @ 25 gm acre⁻¹, acetamaprid @ 4 ml L⁻¹, methamedofos @ 1.25 ml L⁻¹ and tebuconazole; but all insecticides reduced aphid infestation significantly. (Whitworth and Davis, 2012) [34] conducted an efficacy trial on eight insecticides i.e. Endigo 2.06 ZC @ 4 oz/acre, Quilt Xcel 2.2 SE @ 12 oz/acre, Cobalt 2.54 EC @ 26 oz/acre, Declare @ 1.28 oz/acre, Karate Z @ 1.54 oz/acre, Transform @ 37.5 g/hac, Lorsban @ 263 g/hac and Warrior II @ 35 g/hac against Greenbug (*Schizaphisgraminum*) on wheat in field conditions. Results revealed that effectiveness of all insecticides was not significantly different.

Present study reveals that varying levels of resistance in different wheat cultivars can be used as IPM strategy against wheat aphid *Schizaphisgraminum*; however, in case of incidence and abundance of wheat aphid selective insecticides can be used to manage population under economic injury level in order to reduce damage of yield.

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